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Degradation characterization of induced junction photodiodes under ultraviolet irradiation

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Abstract

Induced junction photodiodes have shown great stability and predictability at visible wavelengths, but they may undergo responsivity changes when exposed to ultraviolet (UV) irradiation. When using induced junction photodiodes in a predictable quantum efficient detector (PQED) with operation range extended to UV, the irradiation hardness of photodiodes is of critical concern. In this study, two different types of induced junction photodiodes, with either oxide or nitride passivation layers, were exposed to UV irradiation at 300 nm, 280 nm, 254 nm and 222 nm wavelengths. Their photocurrent was monitored during the irradiation and their UV and visible range spectral responsivities were compared before and after the irradiation. Our results show excellent stability for the nitride coated photodiodes when irradiated at 300 nm, but clear degradation when irradiated at 280 nm, whereas the oxide coated photodiodes remained stable after irradiation at 280 nm and 254 nm, and degraded only at 222 nm. This significant novel outcome opens the way to extend the predictability of PQED to the previously inaccessible wavelength range from 250 nm to 450 nm.

1. Introduction

Induced junction photodiodes utilize the natural inversion layer created by a dielectric passivation layer containing fixed surface state charges when it is deposited onto a suitable semiconductor substrate [1–3]. Typically, this takes the form of an oxide or nitride layer deposited on a silicon substrate, for example SiO₂ on lightly p-doped silicon. As a result of the surface charges, an np-junction is induced without the need for additional doping process. As with other photodiodes, this creates an inversion layer and a depletion region. When photons of sufficient energy enter this active area, they are absorbed, and electron–hole pairs are formed. The electric field of the depletion region will accelerate electrons and

holes in opposite directions, allowing the production of a photocurrent. Because this flow of charge carriers is related to the rate of the incoming photons in a predictable way, measuring the photocurrent provides a reliable absolute measure of the photon flux, from which the optical power of the incoming radiation can be deduced [4–7].

Induced junction photodiodes offer advantages in metrology applications when compared to conventional doped photodiodes: their natural inversion layer avoids doping by impurity atoms, leading to reduced charge-carrier recombination losses due to lack of crystal defects. Furthermore, they have very low surface recombination losses, and crucially, due to their relatively simple structure, their spectral responsivity can be reliably modelled using

computer simulations [8, 9]. This makes induced junction photodiodes predictable and suitable for use in predictable quantum efficient detectors (PQEDs) [4–7].

In PQEDs, induced junction photodiodes are carefully prepared and set in a reflection trap configuration to minimize reflection losses [10, 11], and they have voltage biasing applied to expand the depletion region which minimizes recombination losses. Due to the properties of induced junction photodiodes, the responsivity model, and the PQED configuration, PQEDs provide metrologically robust, low uncertainty, traceable means for measuring optical power of visible light. They have also been shown to be temporally stable over a period of ten years [12].

The PQED is now considered an absolute radiometer defined in the *mise en pratique* for the realization of the candela [7]. However, use of PQED is generally limited to visible and near-IR radiation, as measurements in the ultraviolet (UV) range may suffer from responsivity changes due to UV photons degrading the performance of induced junction photodiodes. Measuring UV radiation with PQED nevertheless remains a highly desired option as a primary standard for responsivity in UV, which is important for maintaining accurate standards in various applications utilizing UV radiation. The core objective of this work is to pave the way for these applications by investigating the UV-stability of induced junction photodiodes and thereby furthering the development of UV-compatible PQEDs.

2. Methodology

Two types of induced junction photodiodes were used for the experiments. Photodiodes of the first type were produced in the chipS-CALe project [11] and had a stack of 6 nm thick silicon oxide and 60 nm thick silicon nitride layer on top of the high-resistivity silicon wafer. Photodiodes of the second type were produced in the Qu-candela project [4, 5] and had either a 220 nm or 300 nm thick silicon oxide layer on top of the high-resistivity silicon wafer. Additionally, the commercially available Hamamatsu S1337 photodiode [13] was used as a benchmark for performance of other types of photodiodes often used as reference detectors.

Except for the Hamamatsu photodiodes, all photodiodes were operated with 5 V reverse bias voltage during the irradiation and the responsivity measurements. The Qu-candela photodiodes have an active area of 22 mm × 11 mm. The chipS-CALe and Hamamatsu photodiodes have an active area of about 10 mm × 10 mm. All photodiodes are mounted behind a circular aperture of 10 mm in diameter. The dark signals of the detectors in the responsivity measurements were typically around 1 nA for Hamamatsu photodiodes and 15 nA for the Qu-candela photodiodes.

Figure 1. Normalized spectra of the radiation sources used in the UV irradiation.

To investigate the change in responsivity of the photodiodes due to the UV exposure, their spectral responsivity was measured before and after irradiation. These measurements were performed by comparing the photodiodes with reference photodetectors built from S1337 photodiodes.

The irradiation was performed using four different wavelengths: 300 nm, 280 nm, 254 nm and 222 nm. The UV irradiation setup consisted of a UV radiation source and a lens to collimate the beam onto the photodiode. For 300 nm and 280 nm, custom LED-based [14] setups were used, whereas 254 nm and 222 nm irradiation used an Amalgam [15] and an Excimer lamp [16], respectively. The stability of irradiation power was $\pm 3\%$ for the Amalgam lamp over 8 d, and $\pm 1\%$ for the Excimer lamp over 2 d. The beam shape was monitored using a beam profiler. The full widths at half maximum of the irradiation spectra, shown in figure 1, were 3 nm, 1 nm, 10 nm, and 15 nm for 222 nm, 254 nm, 280 nm and 300 nm, respectively. The photocurrent signal from the photodiode was monitored during the irradiation to provide real-time information on the condition of the photodiode.

In the first responsivity measurement setup, shown in figure 2, different laser beams with wavelengths ranging from 325 nm to 647 nm were used [17]. The beam was focused, stabilized, and attenuated using a series of mirrors, a laser power controller (LPC), pinholes and a filter wheel. The laser beam diameter ranged from 0.8 mm at 405 nm to 1.1 mm at 647 nm. The beam was directed at the detectors, and the signal from each detector was recorded in the computer. An automated XY translation stage moved the detectors in and out of the beam in turn. This was repeated ten times for both detectors in each set of measurements. To monitor the intensity and stability of the beam, a beam splitter was used to take a portion of the beam and feed it into a monitor detector. Each measurement series also included dark signal measurements to correct the signal.

In the second setup, closely spaced wavelengths of radiation from Xenon and Tungsten lamps were

selected using a monochromator [18]. This setup allows for measurements at a large number of wavelengths ranging from 250 nm to 900 nm. As with the first setup, an automated stage moved the photodiode and the reference detector in and out of the beam. The monochromator beam size was 3 mm × 5 mm.

The laser measurements were performed with an optical power of approximately 200 μW, whereas the monochromator measurements had a power level of 1 μW or less. The responsivity of the studied photodiodes is known to remain linear within 0.1% in our measurement conditions [19]. The laser setup is limited to specific wavelengths but typically has lower uncertainty than the monochromator setup.

The uncertainty evaluation is made for the change of the ratio of test and reference detector signals before and after irradiation. The uncertainty of the laser setup was estimated from reproducibility based on the difference between separate sets of measurements done before UV exposure and from the repeatability of ratio measurements after UV exposure. Several reproducibility tests were performed before the irradiation with the test detector. The reproducibility uncertainty includes effects such as the photodiode alignment, which are counted only once in the combined standard uncertainty. An example of such uncertainty budget is shown in table 1. Similar uncertainty budgets apply to all responsivity ratio measurements.

Similar considerations are valid for the monochromator setup. The main component of uncertainties in the responsivity ratio measurements is the reproducibility of measurements of the test detectors. The effects contributing to the measurement reproducibility include repeatability of ratio measurement

in each scan, temperature, stray light, beam displacement, interreflections and electrical calibrations.

3. Results

3.1. Irradiation between 300 nm and 254 nm

ChipS-CALe and Qu-candela photodiodes showed excellent stability when irradiated at 300 nm. When pre-irradiated with an absorbed dose of 3 J cm⁻² at 300 nm, the responsivity of the ChipS-CALe photodiodes changed up to 0.3% in the UV range. However, after the pre-irradiation the change in responsivity was less than 0.1% in the spectral range from 300 nm to 800 nm between irradiation doses of 3 J cm⁻² and 30 J cm⁻² [20]. It was further observed that a pre-irradiation dose of 1 J cm⁻² was not enough to stabilize the responsivity.

Exposing the photodiodes to radiation at 280 nm wavelength showed a clear difference in their response, as can be seen in figure 3 which shows the normalized signals from a chipS-CALe and a Qu-candela photodiode while being irradiated. This Qu-candela photodiode had an oxide layer thickness of 220 nm. The signal from the Qu-candela photodiode changed by less than 0.3% during the 280 nm irradiation even after an absorbed dose of 5 J cm⁻², whereas the chipS-CALe photodiode signal diminished rapidly over 5% after a much smaller dose of 0.2 J cm⁻². The absorbed doses are calculated from incident dose by considering the reflectances of 70% and 50% of chipS-CALe and Qu-candela photodiodes, respectively.

To investigate whether the irradiation had affected the responsivity of the Qu-candela photodiode, the spectral responsivities before and after irradiation

Table 1. Uncertainty budget for the relative responsivity measurements based on the ratio between the test and reference detector responsivities.

Laser wavelength	Uncertainty of responsivity ratio before irradiation (%)	Uncertainty of responsivity ratio after irradiation (%)	Combined standard uncertainty (%)	Expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) (%)
647 nm	0.08	0.01	0.08	0.15
543 nm	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.09
488 nm	0.09	0.04	0.10	0.20
442 nm	0.09	0.03	0.09	0.18
405 nm	0.20	0.11	0.23	0.45
325 nm	0.11	0.16	0.19	0.39

Figure 6. Relative change in the spectral responsivity of a Qu-candela photodiode measured before and after the irradiation with an absorbed dose of 45 J cm^{-2} at 254 nm. The overall changes are small and within the expanded uncertainty presented in table 1 for the laser measurements.

were compared in the wavelength range from 300 nm to 900 nm. Results are shown in figure 4 for a Qu-candela photodiode with 220 nm thick oxide layer. As can be seen, the maximum observed change in responsivity is less than 0.6%. For most wavelengths, the changes are within the uncertainties, suggesting that the UV irradiation had no distinguishable effects on the responsivity at any of the studied wavelengths.

The results are similar for another Qu-candela photodiode with a 300 nm thick oxide layer that was irradiated at a shorter wavelength of 254 nm: the signal during irradiation, shown in figure 5, indicated

no significant change in the photodiode even after an absorbed dose of 45 J cm^{-2} . The reflectance of the photodiode at 254 nm was 60%.

To investigate whether the responsivity of the photodiode had nevertheless changed as a result of the irradiation, the responsivity was measured again and compared to the responsivity measured before irradiation. As is shown in figure 6, no discernible change in responsivity was observed at any of the measured wavelengths. This shows that the photodiode was not damaged by the 254 nm irradiation.

3.2. Irradiation at 222 nm

As an additional measure to find the limits of the photodiode, another 300 nm oxide layer Qu-candela photodiode was irradiated at 222 nm, which was thought very likely to damage the photodiode. The Hamamatsu photodiode was used as a benchmark for comparing the performance under UV irradiation [21]. As was expected, a significant change appeared in the monitoring signal, as shown in figure 7. The Qu-candela photodiode signal first decreases, then increases, until it finally starts collapsing fast after an absorbed dose of about 11 J cm^{-2} . The Hamamatsu photodiode stays more stable, with its signal only slightly increasing even at much higher doses. The reflectances are 50% and 43% for Qu-candela and Hamamatsu photodiodes, respectively.

When attempting to measure the responsivity of the Qu-candela photodiode after irradiation, it was noticed that centring the beam based on the signal was difficult, as it showed an unusual behaviour: The responsivity was high at the edges and low at the centre. To investigate this effect, the active area of the photodiode was scanned horizontally (X) and vertically (Y), with the result shown in figure 8. The scan revealed that there was irradiation damage localized

to the region most affected by the irradiation. The area of the detector at the centre of irradiation was less responsive, down to less than 30% of the maximum responsivity, indicating damage due to the UV irradiation at 222 nm wavelength. Before irradiation, the responsivity of the active area was uniform within 1% or better, similar to the photodiode profile shown in figure 9. The profile of the irradiation damage matches with the irradiation beam profile shown in figure 10.

The Qu-candela photodiode degradation showed a non-linear effect where the change in responsivity was higher when measuring at higher laser power: The larger the incoming optical power, the lower the responsivity of the detector. For example, as is shown in figure 8, the loss of responsivity was about 70% when the incident optical power was 50 μ W. But at a low incident power of 10 μ W, the loss of responsivity was only 10%.

It is nevertheless notable that the Qu-candela photodiode signal in figure 7 remained within $\pm 3\%$ from the initial signal until a relatively large dose, and the more UV-resistant conventional Hamamatsu photodiode was also damaged by 222 nm irradiation, as shown in figure 11. The measurement results show that responsivity of the Hamamatsu photodiode was degraded by the 222 nm irradiation, despite the detector signal

Figure 11. Spectral responsivity changes of the Hamamatsu S1337 photodiode after irradiation at 222 nm.

being relatively stable or increasing during irradiation. The degradation is seen especially at shorter wavelengths.

4. Summary and conclusion

PQEDs offer a user-friendly and reliable way to measure optical power, but for their predictability at short wavelengths they require induced junction photodiodes that do not become degraded when exposed to UV radiation. In our study, we exposed some induced junction photodiodes to different wavelengths of UV radiation and investigated the resulting changes in their responsivity. We found a novel result that the responsivity of a SiO₂ coated photodiode of type Qu-candela [4, 5] remained unchanged down to irradiation wavelength of 254 nm even with a high absorbed dose of 45 J cm⁻², whereas the performance of another type of induced junction photodiode, coated with silicon nitride, degraded already at 280 nm irradiation.

Specifically, the responsivity of the induced junction photodiodes was measured before and after the UV irradiation in a range of wavelengths from 280 nm to 900 nm. The silicon nitride coated chipS-CALe photodiodes [11] showed an excellent stability when irradiated at wavelengths of 300 nm or larger. However, a clear loss in their responsivity was observed with an absorbed dose of 0.2 J cm⁻² at 280 nm, whereas the Qu-candela photodiode showed no change even after 5 J cm⁻² of absorbed dose at 280 nm. Another Qu-candela photodiode was irradiated at 254 nm with an absorbed dose up to 45 J cm⁻² and its responsivity again showed no change. Finally, a third Qu-candela photodiode was irradiated at 222 nm, and showed a clear reduction of signal and change in responsivity after an absorbed dose of 11 J cm⁻².

Based on these results, the Qu-candela photodiodes remain unchanged by UV irradiation until exposed to photons of a sufficiently high energy. This threshold photon energy is between 5.6 eV and

4.9 eV, corresponding to the 222 nm and 254 nm wavelengths.

In many calibration measurements utilizing PQEDs, two important experimental parameters are the beam diameter and beam power, and it is therefore convenient to illustrate how the irradiation doses relate to them. A 240 h exposure by a 100 μW light beam with 10 mm diameter at 254 nm would result in the above-mentioned 45 J cm⁻² dose for the area affected by the beam. The 11 J cm⁻² dose at 222 nm would correspond to a 50 h exposure. These figures illustrate that at ordinarily available UV power levels from monochromator sources the irradiation times to reach the above doses are very long.

PQEDs have already proven their predictability [9] and stability [12] in the visible range, and suitable UV-resistant induced junction photodiodes would likely enable a significant extension in the PQED operation range into UV wavelengths. Our research demonstrates that Qu-candela induced junction photodiodes fit such criteria, and using them in a PQED would allow for extension in the operation range down to at least 254 nm when combined with the responsivity modelling necessary for PQEDs [22, 23]. This extension is a significant achievement as it opens access to experiments for completely covering the interesting features in spectral responsivity between 270 nm and 290 nm, corresponding to photon energies from 4.2 eV to 4.6 eV [22].

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